

CONTROL OF UNDERGROUND WATER IN THE MINE, DETECTION AND PREVENTION OF RISKS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648010>

Abstract: Measuring the level of underground water and determining its direction play an important role in mining. When a water-level observation well is to be installed, a jet tube terminating in a bit is advanced into the ground as the material is loosened by the jetting action of the water and agitation of the bit. The loosened material is washed to the land surface through the annular space between the jet tube and the wall of the hole. On emerging from the hole, the jetting fluid is channeled into a pit, where the larger particles settle to the bottom, and then into a connecting reservoir pit. The muddy water from the second pit is recirculated through the jet tube and back to the land surface, thereby conserving water and at the same time plastering the sides of the hole with a mud layer that helps to prevent caving. When the desired depth is reached, the hole is flushed «lean with clear water. A pipe with strainer attached is lowered inside the jet tube before the jet tube is extracted. After the resulting well has been developed by surging and pumping, the space around the pipe is filled in. When a small-diameter production well would be satisfactory for use in making an aquifer test, one can be installed by coupling a length of pipe to a jet point and advancing it into the ground by the jetting process. When the desired depth has been reached, the resulting well is completed by surging and pumping. The jetting equipment can be used to obtain subsurface geologic information. It also has proved to be useful for both cleaning large-diameter wells and pumping water from them

Keywords: Geological model, Vibrating-wire piezometers, Terminology, piezometer/inclinometer completions, Groundwater monitoring.

Introduction

Groundwater can have a detrimental effect on slope stability. Fluid pressure acting within discontinuities and pore spaces in the rock mass reduces the effective stress, with a consequent reduction in shear strength. As noted in picture, these aspects are usually the only element of a slope design that can readily be modified by artificial intervention, usually dewatering and depressurisation. However, dewatering and depressurisation measures are usually capital-intensive, require operator commitment to be implemented

effectively and require significant lead\ times in design and implementation. The identification and characterisation of the hydrogeological regime in the early stages of any project is therefore of paramount importance, requiring a well-organised approach to collecting the data and building the conceptual hydrogeological model. The development of a conceptual hydrogeological model to support a slope design analysis and depressurisation program is addressed in picture. This section focuses on the field tests and procedures used to collect the raw hydrogeological data. It describes the basic approaches to data collection then outlines the nature of each appropriate test method.

Initial data collection

The initial step in the hydrogeological data collection program may involve the following.

*A literature search to determine any pertinent hydrogeological information in the region surrounding the project area.

*Identification of existing observation or groundwater production wells within or surrounding the project area, with their completion and stratigraphical details; measurement of groundwater levels in any accessible observation wells; and collection of any pumping data from available production wells. In all cases, it is important to know which formations are being measured or abstracted from.

*Collection of hydrogeological data 'piggy-backed' on mineral exploration and resource drilling programs. Data collection may include:

- _ measurement of groundwater levels in the open drill holes at regular intervals during and after drilling;
- _ collection of water flow rate and other parameters at regular intervals during air drilling;
- _ noting of loss of drilling fluids during water or mud drilling;
- _ injection testing or airlift recovery testing to provide initial permeability information for individual holes.

Note that the use of drilling additives to help stabilize the walls of the hole or increase recovery can alter the permeability around the hole and compromise the quality of the data.

*Installation of groundwater observation wells using holes drilled for the geology resource evaluation or geotechnical programs.

*Implementation of a routine water level monitoring program in all available groundwater observation wells or piezometers. For a new project, measurement

of water levels on a weekly basis would be the standard procedure, possibly reducing to monthly with time as more data are collected.

* Implementation of a hydrological database, which can be expanded as the project proceeds. Many operators use one database for all pit slope hydrogeological data, general dewatering and environmental management systems. In some cases the database is integrated with the geological modelling, geotechnical database and mine planning programs.

Characterisation of the overall groundwater flow system

* Injection testing or airlift recovery testing during drilling, to provide more detailed permeability information.

* Installation of test pumping wells, and carrying out pumping tests to characterise permeability and storage characteristics and to assess the groundwater flow characteristics over a wider area.

* Hydrochemical sampling and analysis of observation wells and pumping wells to characterise variations in groundwater quality which may help with the interpretation of the groundwater flow system.

Terminology

The terms ‘observation well’ and ‘piezometer’ are commonly used to describe drill holes that are used for measuring water levels or pore pressures in the field. The terms are often synonymous although, in many texts and reports, ‘piezometer’ is often used for installations with shorter, sealed completion intervals. Picture 1 shows how observation wells and piezometers may be installed as standpipes or grouted instruments. It also shows how vibrating-wire piezometers may be grouted in place to measure pore pressures at point intervals. The term ‘monitoring well’ is synonymous with ‘observation well’ but is often used to describe wells installed primarily for water chemistry sampling.

Picture 1. Alternative piezometer installations in core or DR drill holes
Standpipe piezometers

The traditional piezometer is a standpipe that allows pressure to be measured as a head of water in a pipe. The piezometer consists of a filter tip or perforated interval of pipe of a desired length attached to the bottom of an impermeable casing that rises to the surface. The perforated interval is isolated by an upper seal, typically with grout placed above the seal to the surface (Picture 1). The level to which the water rises in the pipe indicates the average pressure over the perforated interval. In the early stages of groundwater investigation, if piezometers are used in preference to open holes the perforated interval of the piezometer may be long (35+ m), so the average head of a formation is measured. As the investigation becomes more focused, a shorter (5 m or less) perforated interval may be installed in subsequent holes to measure the pressure at more discrete depths.

Vibrating-wire piezometers

Vibrating-wire piezometers consist of a vibrating-wire sensing element in a protective steel housing. The sensing element consists of a tensioned steel wire clamped to both ends of a hollow cylindrical body. The piezometer converts water pressure to a frequency signal via a diaphragm, the tensioned steel wire and an electromagnetic coil. When excited by the electromagnetic coil the wire vibrates at its natural frequency. The piezometer is designed so that a change in pressure on the diaphragm causes a change in tension of the wire, altering its natural frequency of vibration. The vibration of the wire in the proximity of the coil generates a signal that is transmitted to the readout device. The readout device processes the signal, applies calibration factors and displays a reading. Vibrating-wire piezometers are a good method of collecting water level data and defining vertical hydraulic gradients around active pit slopes. Multiple transducers may be set in alternating bentonite/sand packs placed using a tremie pipe. Alternatively, a string of three or more vibrating-wire piezometer instruments may be grouted directly into the hole without the use of a filter pack. Grouted vibrating-wire installations are more applicable in settings with low permeability. Because there is no standpipe and therefore no water in the completed hole, there are no well-bore storage effects and the initial equilibration response time of the piezometers is much faster. Picture 2 shows a multiple grouted-in vibrating-wire installation where seven piezometers were installed in an H diamond hole.

Picture 2(a,b). a) Example of a multiple vibrating-wire piezometer installation in a core hole. b) Example of dual piezometer/inclinometer installation

Joint piezometer, inclinometer completions

At some operations it has been possible to install completions acting jointly as standpipe piezometers and inclinometers, as illustrated in Picture 2(b). monitoring needs to be isolated and sealed. There are two practical ways to achieve this. The first is to use a packer system and to grout the annulus above the packer. The second is to grout vibrating-wire transducers into place, as shown in Picture 3. In this process, the grout tube shown in Picture 3 must be extended so that the grout is introduced at the end of the hole. The second option allows multiple sensors to be installed within the hole. An issue with horizontal drilling is that the weight of the drill string often causes the holes to 'droop' (deviate downward) during drilling. This would affect subsequent vibrating-wire piezometer readings because the instruments may actually be lower than the target elevation. Therefore, if the intent is to install piezometers, it is beneficial if the hole can be directionally surveyed prior to piezometer installation.

Picture 3. Vibrating-wire piezometers installed from the pit slope or from underground.

Guidance notes: installation of test wells for pit slope depressurisation

It is not the intention of this chapter to provide detailed drilling procedures for pumping wells. However, there are three important guidelines to follow for successful installation of test pumping wells in fractured rock settings.

1. Consider the installation of small-diameter pilot holes to establish ground conditions prior to completing high-cost production wells.
2. Minimise the use of drilling mud; if the use of mud is unavoidable, adapt the well design accordingly.
- 3 Use an appropriate well screen and filter-pack design for the application of the well

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